

PSYCHOLINGUISTICS AND ITS BRIEF HISTORY

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Annotation

This article is about the history of the emergence of psycholinguistics, which is one of the branches of linguistics. Psycholinguistics is a relatively new area of study, though interest in the mind-language relationship has a long history. And here we mentioned some prominent scientists and their works.

It is a field formed on the basis of connections between psychology and linguistics. The term "psycholinguistics" was first used in the USA in 1946 by N. Pronko and popularized in 1953 at a scientific conference held at Indiana University. Currently, there are theories and methods related to psycholinguistics in different countries of the world. Psycholinguistics is a scientific study of the formation and hearing aspects of speech as a complex system and structure related to the development of society and the individual. The main study topic of psycholinguistics is the formation of speech, its conscious listening and perception, and the formation of children's speech. According to the foreign teaching of psycholinguistics, there is a different definition. Psycholinguistics defines language and speech as a reflection of the nature and structure of the human mind. Psycholinguistics scientifically studies the psychology of the speaker and the listener, its dependence on the conditions of simple and passionate states, the relationship with the structure of the text, diseases associated with various speech disorders (aphasia).

At the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century, the language was considered as a system that existed in the context of real speech activity and was frozen. Many scientists, who consider speech as the implementation of this system, remove it from the subject of linguistics and consider it a subject of psychology. According to the famous psychologist S.L. Rubenstein, "Speech has only a psychological aspect." Such a view cannot be applied to language. Language is a means of communication between people, informs about the processes in society, and has the ability to influence the listener to a certain extent. We know that the possibility of language cannot be realized without speech and speech activity. and the unity of thinking is expressed in speech. Speech exists in oral and written form, in which our thought enters a material form." Written and oral speech, which is considered the main means of interaction between people, is the most complex form of speech activity that

depends on psychology. Written and spoken speech are very different from each other in terms of their occurrence, development method, and psychological approaches.

It is known that oral speech is formed in a person first of all. Oral speech occurs directly in the process of live communication. Psycholinguistic theory was formed on the basis of the psychological approach to speech of the scientist L.S.Vygotsky, who was engaged in the study of speech activity. According to V.P.Belyanin, "Psycholinguistics is the science of the laws of formation and acceptance of speech expression." Therefore, psycholinguistics, along with linguistics, studies the psychological mechanisms of speech activity, such as the formation and acceptance of speech. Speech, as a functional system, involves different areas of the brain structure in speech activity. We know that brain swelling, brain hemorrhage, inflammation and similar injuries occur as a result of mental illnesses in many people. People with brain damage cannot understand other people's speech. In order to study this situation and find a solution to it, not only neurosurgery, but also the science of linguistics is necessary. It is necessary to determine how speech is constructed, according to which mechanisms speech activity is carried out. As a result, the science of neurolinguistics emerged as part of the science of psycholinguistics. As a separate field of knowledge, neurolinguistics began to form in the 50s and 60s of the 20th century, the emergence of this science was based on the practical requirements of aphasiology, which is a branch of medicine dealing with the treatment of aphasia. The science of neurolinguistics has been studied by many researchers. The interpretations of neurolinguistics are based on the researches of I.M.Sechenov. According to Baudouin de Courtenay, "Psychic phenomena cannot be separated from the physiological substrate, so they can all exist only with a living brain. Neurolinguistics studies the mechanisms of speech activity in the brain and the changes that occur in speech processes as a result of local damage to the brain. The main stages of the emergence and development of the science of neurolinguistics are associated with the name of Alexander Romanovich Luria, the founder of neuropsychology and neurolinguistics.

During his life, A.Luria studied the problems of speech: its ontogeny, functions, disorders, brain structure, and gave information about them in "Очерки психофизиологии письма", "Основные проблемы неуролингвистики", "Очерки психофизиологии письма" "Язык и сознание" and other works. In the book "Ocherki psychophysiology pisma" published in 1950 by A.Luria and in the monograph "Язык и сознание" he mentions the role of speech in the formation of human consciousness and considers it a new aspect of the research

problem. A.Luria's monograph is mainly neurolinguistic in nature, he compares his linguistic research on the function and structure of speech with neuropsychological data on the differences in the forms of speech perception and speech comprehension disorders as a result of local damage to the brain. He emphasizes that observing and studying speech phenomena is more complicated than studying children's speech. The causes and manifestations of speech defects are different. The study of speech impairment requires the researcher to acquire a set of knowledge related not only to linguistics and psychology, but also to human physiology and medicine.

Conclusion

Psycholinguistics is a fast-growing field of study which has contributed enormously over the past 50 years to our understanding of language as a phenomenon. Although many of our scientists have made scientific works and innovations in this linguistic branch, there are still many presumptions that no one has investigated. Psycholinguists need to do more to build contacts with those who share their preoccupation with language in use.

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